

Unveiling “Socio-Religious Reform Movements” in the early 19th Century Bengal through Krishna Mohan Banerjea’s play *The Persecuted*

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Abstract: This paper examines the socio-religious reform movements that unfolded in early 19th-century Bengal, as exemplified in the inaugural Indian drama in English, "The Persecuted or Dramatic Scenes Illustrative of Present State of Hindu Society in Calcutta (1831)." The inquiry revolves around defining the Socio-religious reform movement, highlighting its advocacy for changes in social behavior and its tradition of protest and dissent as vehicles for societal and religious reform. The analysis establishes that "The Persecuted" carries distinct overtones of the socio-religious reform movement, predominantly conveyed through the character 'Banylal,' the play's protagonist. The paper concludes by asserting that the acts of breaking dietary taboos and opposing superstitions within the play serve as vivid reflections of the Socio-religious reform movement prevalent in early 19th-century Bengal.

Introduction: This article explores the response of Krishna Mohan Banerjea, an early Indian playwright in English, through his play "The Persecuted or Dramatic Scenes Illustrative of the Present State of Hindoo Society in Calcutta" (1831), to the socio-religious movements and prevailing trends of the early 19th century. Notably, "The Persecuted" holds the distinction of being recognized as the first English drama written in India, with its publication dating back to 1831.

Methodology of research: The chosen research methodology is qualitative, incorporating textual analysis. The identified text will undergo a comprehensive review and analysis within the historical and cultural framework of early 19th-century Bengal society. The recent restoration of the play “*The Persecuted*”, edited by Somadatta Mandal is the primary source. The other works cited are the secondary sources.

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- i. **Socio-religious reform movement:** According to Kenneth W. Jones, “ A Socio Religious movement, advocated modifications in social behavior, justified such advocacy by one or another form of religious authority, and then built an organizational structure it maintained over time” (Jones Kenneth.W,2). A socio-religious reform movement is a collective endeavor that seeks to instigate changes in social behavior by challenging and opposing established social norms, practices, and beliefs within a particular religious framework. These movements often encounter resistance and protest from adherents of the existing religious beliefs, as the reformers express dissent during their initial phases. The primary aim of such movements is to reform and transform societal practices deemed outdated or unjust, and they are driven by a desire to bring about positive changes in the way individuals and communities interact within the context of their religious and social affiliations. With this understanding, the play *The Persecuted* is studied in this paper.
- ii. **Reformist traditions in the early 19th Century-Bengal:**

The play mirrors the events in Calcutta, making it imperative to grasp the political landscape of early 19th-century India during the East India Company's dominion. The East India Company, adhering to a "policy of non-interference" until the significant Charter Act of 1813, refrained from meddling in the socio-cultural and religious affairs of the native population. The appointment of William Bentinck as the Governor-general of India marked a shift, with the British government, influenced by Christian missionaries, permitting those inclined to "civilize" Indians, deeming them primitive. Additionally, the company was mandated to allocate a lakh rupees annually to revive literature, promote scientific knowledge among Indians, and support learned Indian natives. Consequently, Christian missionaries and reform-oriented officials initiated the process of reforming and westernizing Indian society.

The response of Indian natives to these reforms was diverse. While the elite perceived them as a conspiracy to convert Indians to Christianity, some young individuals embraced Westernization. As previously mentioned, the initial phase of these socio-religious movements instigated changes in social behavior. Bengali society experienced significant influences from the colonial agenda aimed at educating and westernizing natives. Consequently, the 19th century in

India witnessed an amalgamation of the culture of native Indians and the Western values of the English.

The transformation in Bengali society was conspicuous, characterized by three main traditions within the Bengal Renaissance. The reformative tradition, led by Raja Ram Mohan Roy, constituted the first. The second tradition was the radical movement of the Young Bengal Movement, influenced by Henry Louis Vivian Derozio. Lastly, the revivalist tradition emerged under the influence of the teachings of Ramakrishna Parama Hamsa.

Raja Rammohan Roy, acknowledged as the father of modern India, established the Brahmo Samaj in 1828 and initiated a systematic campaign against polytheism, the sati superstition, and the caste system. While protesting against superstitions and social evils like Sati, he was not inherently against Hinduism or Brahmanism.

The revivalist tradition, stemming from the teachings of Ramakrishna Paramahansa, aimed to regenerate ancient Hindu Society, considering it philosophically and culturally superior to any other religion. Rejecting acculturative trends from westernization, this tradition added rationality to existing religious practices.

Derozio's teachings were a crucial component of another school, the radical Hindu college tradition, whose main output, the Young Bengal Movement, presented numerous convincing arguments for the social behavior changes advocated by the socio-religious reform movement and the British Raj's civilizing goal. As Kenneth W. Zones describes, interactions of civilizations give rise to traditions of protest as well as dissent in the process of socio-religious movement:

“British introduced their own version of western civilization as they gained control of South Asia in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. By the nineteenth century, three layers of civilization interacted and moulded the socio-religious movements of that century. Each civilization contained its own tradition of protest and dissent that provided the basic past framework for socio-religious movements of the British period.” (Jones Kenneth.W: 2)

The evolution of British educational policy and the role of Hindu College in disseminating Western education in India are well-documented. Therefore, understanding the

impact of the establishment of Hindoo College and the Derozian group, which challenged orthodox Hindu religious practices and customs through English education, becomes crucial.

Hindoo College gave rise to a radical trend known as the "Young Bengal Movement," inspired by Henry Vivian Derozio. Teaching at Hindoo College from 1826 to 1831, Derozio, born in 1809, embraced radical ideologies influenced by the French Revolution. Despite his youth, he proved to be an exceptional teacher, attracting a large number of gifted and devoted students. Derozio encouraged his students to think critically, challenge authority, uphold principles of liberty, equality, and freedom, and revere truth.

The Derozians, as a group, boldly confronted the deficiencies of contemporary socio-religious authorities through reasoned arguments. Embracing liberal views and strong ideals, they rebelled against conventional wisdom and religious orthodoxy, advocating for independence in all aspects of westernization, including thought, dietary choices, and alcohol consumption. As Srinivas Iyengar notes, "The Derozians became a law unto themselves," (Iyengar, 40) dressing, eating, and drinking in the manner of the Englishmen.

While the Derozians and the students of Hindoo College, with their radical views, did not fully crystallize into a mature socio-religious movement, they expressed their dissent on religious orthodoxy through print and literature. Examining the influence of Hindoo College on early 19th-century socio-religious reform movements, this paper explores the first Indian English play, "The Persecuted or Dramatic Scenes Illustrative of the Present State of Hindoo Society in Calcutta," written by Dr. Rev. Krishna Mohan Banerjea (1813-85).

iii. **Krishna Mohan Banerjea's Biography- Young Bengal Movement:**

Krishna Mohan Banerjea was born on May 24, 1813, in Shyampur, Kolkata, to the conservative Kulin Brahmin parents Sreemati Devi and Jibon Krishna Banerjea. Coming from an orthodox background, his formal education commenced with Shasthrik rituals at the age of five. He began attending David Hare's 'School Society Institution' in Kalitala at six, and later, due to his recognized talent, David Hare brought him to his school at Pataldanga.

Krishna Mohan achieved notable academic success, securing a scholarship that led to his admission to the newly founded Hindoo College in Calcutta in 1824. Unfortunately, at the age of fifteen, Krishna Mohan lost his father, but he persevered in his studies, relying on scholarships.

His educational journey at Hindoo College involved the study of Sanskrit and English, where he excelled and won prizes in various cultural competitions.

In 1829, Krishna Mohan Banerjea graduated from Hindoo College with the top rank in his class. He subsequently joined David Hare's Patal Danga School as an assistant teacher, dedicating two years to this role. In 1827, at the age of 17, Derozio, a mentor for the Young Bengal movement and a figure associated with Hindoo College student rebels, was appointed.

"Banerjea is four years junior to Derozio , and Derozio never taught him in the classrooms. Derozio used to participate in informal reading circles with Krishna Mohan, Ram Gopal Ghose, Peary Chand Mitra, Rasik Krishna Mallik, and Dakshina Ranjan Mukerjea, who founded the Academic Association debating club.. These reading circles are usually held at Krishna Mohan's house on Guruprasad Choudhury Lane, north of the college. As Professor Anand Lal gives biographical details of Krishna Mohan Banerjea, describes how the playwright and his friends were influenced by Derozio: "Derozio instilled in them a spirit of critical enquiry, which led to their questioning of the conservative Hindu Society of their background, even though Banerjea himself came from upper caste Brahmin lineage." (Lal; P.17)

Krishna Mohan's engagement and conversations with Derozio in these casual reading circles had a profound impact on his worldview. Together with the Young Bengalis, Krishna Mohan developed a sense of skepticism regarding the existence of God and began to critically examine those who sanctioned Hindu customs and dietary practices. Their inquiries extended to challenging Hindu taboos related to consuming prohibited foods and alcoholic beverages, questioning the unquestionable authority of those responsible for formulating these prohibitions.

- iv. **Summary:** This play unfolds across five acts, introducing twenty-three characters, with Banylal serving as the central protagonist. A member of the Young Bengal Movement, Banylal's education and exposure to Western influences lead him to question the hypocritical Brahmin-sanctioned system. Defying the societal norms set by the Brahmins, he engages in acts such as consuming meat and alcohol.

The discovery of Banylal's actions by an old servant appalls him, prompting a report to Mahadeb, Banylal's father and an orthodox Brahmin. This sets the stage for a heated verbal confrontation between father and son. Despite Mahadeb's efforts, including kneeling and pleading for his son to abandon his practices for the sake of family honor, Banylal remains steadfast in his beliefs.

Exploiting the situation, two cunning Brahmins, Turkolankar and ByadhaBhagis, alongside a shrewd newspaper editor named Lallchand, coerce Mahadeb into excommunicating his son in the name of preserving Hindu culture. Some staunch Hindus, Kamdeb, Debnauth, and Ramlochan, align themselves with these Brahmins against the rebellious youths.

Mahadeb resorts to bribery, offering 'Pronamie' to the two Brahmins, resulting in a quarrel over the shared bounty. However, to avoid the ire of religious elders, Mahadeb is compelled to cast out Banylal. Meanwhile, a group of young individuals, not initially part of the Young Bengal movement but liberal in their thinking, discusses the Banylal issue. Overcoming initial hesitations, they join forces with Banylal, Shyamnauth, Chunder Coomar, Indranauth, and others, all committed to continuing the Hindu reformation and challenging bigotry, even at the risk of their lives.

- v. **The conflict of ideologies:** The play unfolds with three distinct groups embodying opposing ideologies, reflecting the diverse facets of Bengali society at the time. The first group comprises Banylal and his Young Bengal associates, vocal critics of Hindu traditions. The second group consists of orthodox Brahmins like Turkolankar and Bydhabhagis, while the third group involves liberal Hindu youth like Bhyrub, Hurrychund, and others, who align with the Young Bengal group by the play's conclusion.

The central theme revolves around the 'conflict' between the Western-educated Young Bengal faction and the ideology of the orthodox Brahmins. Intriguingly, another group, including Mahadeb (Banylal's father) and the young servant, bears the consequences of this clash, being forced to choose between silence or suffering. Notably, the absence of female characters, though reflective of historical societal constraints, may also convey the playwright's intentional omission to suggest that women played no direct role in oppression or reformation.

The play's title, 'The Persecuted or Dramatic Scenes Illustrative of Present State of Hindoo Society in Calcutta,' holds significance as it delves into the persecution of Brahmins in Calcutta society. The narrative exposes not only the persecution of rebels unveiling the hypocrisy of certain revered Brahmins but also the plight of Brahmin followers who view them as authoritative figures in Hindu religion. The playwright employs dramatic scenes from Calcutta society to illustrate the methods of persecution.

Commencing with a conflict between young Bengali ideology and orthodox Hindu beliefs, the play unveils the hypocrisy, corruption, and bigotry within revered Brahmin circles. The authoritative Brahmins and the press exaggerate the activities of the Young Bengal movement to foster hatred among Hindus against the rebellious youth, suppressing dissent. Innocent families suffer the consequences of this conflict. As the play concludes, young individuals with liberal ideas join the rebels, pledging to continue the mission of reforming Hindu society. Notably, both the oppressors and the dissenters are Brahmins, highlighting the societal friction resulting from changing behaviors—a typical feature of Socio-religious reform movements. The playwright aims to inspire Hindu youth to join the dissenting voices in the pursuit of reform.

vi. Violating dietary restrictions:

Hindu College imparted a Western education to the youth, fostering a spirit of inquiry within them. This newfound curiosity led them to question the foundational behavioral norms entrenched in Hindu society. Faced with unsatisfactory answers, they gradually deviated from these established norms. In contrast, the preceding generation, educated in a contrasting manner, struggled to comprehend this emerging thought process. The playwright introduces this ideological divide in the play through the very first dialogue delivered by the young servant.

“The course of nature is indeed inexplicable. Water carries fire within it; and cold emits heat. Our Kurta (the head of the family) spends hours and hours after devotion; my young master –ha! What does he eat beef in his room! Ha! Ha! Ha! Fine contrast-excessive devotion on the one hand, and eating beef in the other! – Kurta’s old servant eats Gopal’s Prosaud; (atables dedicated to Deities) I-supply

my Baboo with bread and meat. Fine indeed; say, very fine until Kurta is ignorant these.” (Banerjea, P.31)

Born into a Brahmin family, the notion of consuming beef was unthinkable in that era. Nevertheless, one must interpret the actions of Bany Lal and his friends through a reformist perspective. In the play, Bany Lal and his companions, products of colonial education, engaged in breaking dietary laws as a mode of dissent against prevailing social norms, all in pursuit of their reformation objectives. As Amit Chaudhury elucidates:

“In nineteenth century Bengal, intellectual and social change was achieved in roughly two ways: “by breaking caste or dietary taboos (by eating beef), and ... by instituting social reform (say, in support of widow remarriage).” However, this bourgeoisie also attempted to recover “the very tradition that, at other times, it seemed intent on redefining or even disowning” (Amit Chaudhuri 3).

In the corresponding scene, as the young servant conveys to Banylal the discovery of his consumption of beef by the old servant, Banylal's response underscores his deliberate defiance of dietary taboos, emphasizing his commitment to instigating social reform. The implication, clearly established in the initial scene, is that the act of consuming beef serves as a form of dissent. Banylal's response can be read below::

“What do I hear? Am I discovered? Well—I am not surprised. I anticipated all that are now transpiring when first I began to feel hostile to Hindooism.—Such occurrences must happen. When knowledge has begun its march, Hindooism must fall and must fall with noise. Reformation must come on and excite heart-burning jealousies among men—Gods! What will my father think when he hears these? What will bigots say when they understand my thoughts and feelings? I fear—I fear not for the bigot's rage and the priest's thunders. But I fear—I fear for my old father....I expected this and am prepared for it—prejudice and liberalism cannot long reign under the same roof without a rupture.” (35)

Hence, he clarified the determination of the Young rebels, indicating that they were resilient enough to confront societal disapproval for their dissent. **Hypocrisy and the truth:** To elucidate his agenda for the reader, Krishna Mohan introduces two avaricious Brahmins named Turkolankar and Bydhabhagis in the subsequent scene, facilitating an intriguing conversation

between them. This dialogue serves the purpose of laying bare the hypocrisy within Brahminism and the prevailing corruption within the priesthood. Both Turkolankar's initial statement and Bydhabhagis' concluding remark echo the sentiment that "being a Brahmin is a great blessing" and "the Brahmin is a blessed one," respectively. This particular scene encapsulates the fundamental challenge faced by the reformers of the Young Bengal movement, resonating not only within the context of the play but also in the broader real-world scenario.

Drawing from Turkolankar's conversation with Bydhabhagis, Krishna Mohan launches a dual assault on Brahminism and the blind reverence exhibited by the common people towards Brahmins: "They call us Gods; as if we had more hands and noses than other people. O how I wish that these asses continue involved in all these prejudices!" (The Persecuted, 36). Bhaidhabhagis complements this discourse with his own perspective: "O what fools they were – they all fell prostrate before me, and having seated me upon an eminence began to bow down and heap my feet with their rupees, annas, and pice. I laid my feet upon their heads and they deemed themselves particularly blessed! Fools!" (37). This serves as a scathing satire on the prevalent practice of innocent Hindus paying and venerating Brahmins as if they were Gods.

Krishna Mohan's audacious endeavor may have been driven by his comprehension of the caste system and its operations. His insight might have been enriched by witnessing the escalating resistance of orthodox Brahmins to reform movements in the early nineteenth century, notably with the ban on Sati in 1829, just two months before the play's publication. While he refrains from directly accusing Brahmins for the caste system, he vehemently disapproves of the attitudes exhibited by religious elders, which, in his view, were regressing compared to their predecessors. Turkolankar, in particular, commends the contemporary Brahmins for exploiting the masses in the guise of religious authority like this: "I think we are better off than Brahmins of old ages. I believe we are much indebted to our predecessors for having paved the way to our advantage. I believe we owe them all the benefits we at the present enjoy." (The Persecuted.37)

"The Persecuted," designed as a philosophical representative of the Young Bengal movement, unveils the methods of exploitation employed by Brahmin pundits in the early nineteenth century. As articulated by Brajranjan Mani, "the task of philosophy, as Marx stated, is not merely to understand the world but also to change material conditions and reconstitute society so that the few are not able to exploit the many" (Mani;21)

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Similar to his fellow members in the Young Bengal Movement, Bany Lal was initially confounded by the paradox of prioritizing familial duties over societal obligations. Nevertheless, he has made the choice to persist in his mission of social reformation.

“A father verses Truth ? –Aye –it is our fate to be hard. We are doomed to suffer all these misfortunes. Truth comes and hardens our feelings. Truth prevents us from yielding to a father’s cries and a mother’s solicitations. Utter a falsehood! Deceive friends and relations by a penance! –My soul shrinks with horror at these reflections. No –a father’s cries are not stronger than those of truth. Bear strong my mind and slacken not. A father may weep; a mother may shed tears, a brother may lament; a sister may repine; but let them not triumph over the truth. A father’s feelings are not more to be consulted than the dictates of TRUTH. Kindred is not trample upon the truth. Bear witness my mind. I neglect a father for her. I break down the chains of filial duty for Truth. Witness this and do me justice. I will bear up all like a man.” (*The Persecuted*, 46)

In portraying the character Bany Lal, Krishna Mohan effectively issued a challenge to Hindu youth, urging them to champion the cause of "truth" derived from liberal education. The assertion that "Brahmins were the blessed ones in society" (39) establishes the pursuit of truth as an act of dissent. This aligns with the common characteristics of a socio-religious movement, where reformers, as noted by Kenneth W. Jones, endeavor to alter the prevailing status quo. Simultaneously, religious authorities seek to thwart reformers' initiatives by imposing their personal agendas through reinterpretations of scriptures. This dynamic is evident in the following excerpt:

“All socio-religious movements demanded changes, ranging from the relatively limited approach of defensive and self-consciously orthodox groups to radicals who articulated a sweeping condemnation of the status quo. The term 'religious' refers to the type of authority used to legitimize a given ideology and its accompanying programme. This authority was based on scriptures that were no longer considered to be properly observed, on a reinterpretation of doctrines, or on scriptural sources arising from the codification of a new religious leader's

message. At times different types of authority were combined to legitimize a particular programme” (Jones p2.)

Consequently, in "The Persecuted," characters like Turkolankar, Bhydhabaghi, and Lal Chand, embodying hypocritical adherence to Hinduism, fortify the religious status quo and disdain Bany Lal's critique of it. These orthodox and hypocritical Hindus, represented by Turkolankar, Bhydhabhagis, and Lal Chand, harbor animosity towards Bany Lal and his group for their dissenting voice, reflecting the socio-religious conditions in early nineteenth-century Bengal.

By drawing parallels between Krishna Mohan's experiences and the scenes enacted in "The Persecuted" by the Bany Lal group, one can discern the alignment of these descriptions. Bany Lal and his radical associates become a source of disdain for figures like Turkolankar, Bhyadhabhagis, and Lal Chand, who express dissent against orthodoxy in the play. While Turkolankar and Bhydhabhagis engage in alcohol consumption, they paradoxically command reverence from ordinary Hindus. Dialogues from Act II, Scene 3 shed light on the nature of their hypocrisy.

“Bydhabhagis. Why, does that puzzle you? I thought you were wiser.— got drunk! Yes, got drunk. Is there any oddity in that? Were you never drunk?

Turkolankar. I do not say I was never; but I never was so publicly.”(*The Persecuted* 48)

This dialogue underscores the reality that orthodox Brahmins harbor disdain for Bany Lal and his group due to their open criticism of established practices. However, this exposes a potential vulnerability in their hypocrisy, jeopardizing their current social standing. As long as Hindus adhere to superstitions, they face no existential threat. This inference is drawn from the following excerpts in their conversation within the same scene:

“Turk. I do not know what you mean- expound a course of shasters and allow drinking! I cannot understand you.

Bydha. Well-that is not my fault. I am not to give you understanding. However, I will help you a little, --You stare at my allowing drinking to them—I am their Guroo –whatever creed I will propose to them they will be bound to observe. –

they never read the shasters, and so did I, but I invented a set of doctrines and recommended to them as their shasters. They are particularly glad the drinking is allowed.”(*The Persecuted*,48)

This illustrates Banerjea's intention to suggest that the priesthood manipulates interpretations at their discretion, keeping the masses uninformed to serve their selfish desires and sustain their livelihood. In the play, Banylal exposes this hypocrisy, emerging as a thorn in the side of the hypocritical orthodox Brahmins. Refusing to conform to his comfort zone and reject the established status quo presented by his father and old servant, Bany Lal advocates for truth. He rejects the notion that "being a Brahmin is a blessing" in the existing society, highlighting the inhumanity of someone being considered less blessed due to their birth in another caste. This reformist approach is not without its perils.

Conclusion:

Krishna Mohan seemingly aimed to convey to Calcutta Society in the 1830s that liberal education had the potential to free them from ignorance and unmask the hypocrisy of influential figures within the Hindu community. Concurrently, he may have sought to encourage a departure from prevalent superstitions. The "truth" unveiled is that Hindu leaders, though publicly opposing westernization and modernization, privately desire these changes for their own children, while they perpetuate ignorance and superstitions among the masses.

Under the influence of Derozio, Krishna Mohan underwent an atheist phase, suggesting that the truth, in his perspective, could not align with any other religion, as Hinduism appeared bigoted and steeped in superstitions propagated by hypocrites. This message was directed explicitly at Hindu youth, including the portrayal of liberal individuals hesitant to join the crusade against Hinduism's bigotry.

In the play's conclusion, Banylal encourages Hindu youth with liberal ideologies to join him despite differing views on certain points. Bhyrub, a liberal Hindu adolescent, emphasizes viewing common responsibilities as men "liberated from the shackles of prejudice" (75). He pledges to be a "devoted servant to the cause of truth and Hindoo reformation" (76). The resolution is to continue their reformation struggle with "perseverance and prudence" as their motto. The play concludes with a call to action for the reform of Hindu society.

Findings: Krishna Mohan's conversion to Christianity, influenced by Alexander Duff shortly after the play's publication, suggests a shift in his beliefs. However, there is no explicit evidence in the play pointing to an alternate religion. The "truth" advocated by Krishna Mohan may signify the imperative need for reformation in Hindu social order or the rejection of superstitions. His expression in the play primarily revolves around dissenting against superstitions and the exploitation of priestly figures leveraging religion for personal gain. The characters like Banyal breaking dietary taboos and acting as rebels signify changes in social behavior, reflecting the environment of the early 19th-century Socio-religious reform movement.

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